

METHODS, WAYS AND TECHNOLOGIES OF ORGANIZING MODERN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Yaqubova Gullola Sharobiddinovna

Andijan Machine Building Institute akademik lyceum english teacher

Annotation: The field of modern foreign language learning has seen significant advancements in methods, ways, and technologies that have transformed the way languages are taught and learned. In this article, we will explore some of the key approaches and tools that are shaping language education today. Organizing modern foreign language learning involves a diverse set of methods, approaches, and technologies aimed at creating engaging, effective, and inclusive learning experiences. Let's delve into a variety of these techniques.

Keywords; Task-Based Language Learning (TBLL), Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Blended Learning, Mobile Learning, Augmented Reality (AR)

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): One of the most widely used methods for teaching modern foreign languages, CLT focuses on the use of authentic communication in the target language. This approach emphasizes the importance of real-life situations and meaningful interaction, allowing students to develop their language skills in a more natural and effective way. This approach emphasizes real-life communication and interaction. It focuses on teaching language as a tool for communication, with an emphasis on meaningful use of language in context. *Communicative Approach* This method focuses on developing speaking and listening skills through real-life communication situations. Learners engage in authentic conversations, discussions, role-plays, and language games to practice using the language in context. *Immersive language learning* Utilizing immersion techniques, such as living in a country where the language is spoken, or

using virtual reality technology and 360° videos to simulate real-life language environments.

Task-Based Language Learning (TBLL): Task-Based Language Learning is a methodology that encourages learning through the completion of specific tasks in the target language. By engaging students in meaningful activities, such as problem-solving or role-playing, TBLL helps learners develop both their language proficiency and their ability to use the language in practical contexts. Learning is structured around the completion of specific tasks, which could be anything from solving a problem to finding information. This approach emphasizes practical language use and real-world application. *Language Exchanges and Tandem Learning* pairing learners who are native speakers of different languages to learn from each other through conversation practice. This approach involves assigning learners with real-world language tasks, such as planning a trip or conducting an interview. Through these tasks, learners acquire language skills as they work towards accomplishing specific goals. *Online platforms and apps* Leveraging language learning platforms and apps like Duolingo, Babbel, Rosetta Stone, and Memrise to access interactive lessons, games, and exercises for specific language learning.

Blended Learning: This approach combines traditional classroom instruction with online resources and tools, providing students with the flexibility to engage with language learning materials both in and outside the classroom. Blended learning also allows for personalized learning experiences, as students can access a variety of multimedia resources and interactive activities to support their language learning journey. *Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL)* this method involves teaching subjects like science, history, or geography in a foreign language. It combines language learning with the learning of content, providing opportunities for authentic language use in various contexts. *Authentic Materials* using authentic texts, videos, and audios (such as news articles, podcasts, and films) from the target language's culture to expose learners to real language use.

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR): Immersive experiences that can transport learners to different cultural and linguistic environments, providing a sense of real-world language use. *Flipped Classroom* model involves learners studying language materials independently outside of the classroom, such as watching videos or using interactive online resources. Classroom time is then dedicated to discussion, practice, and application of the learned content. Incorporating a mix of in-person classroom instruction with online resources, including video conferencing, educational websites, and digital textbooks for a comprehensive language learning experience.

Mobile Learning: With the widespread use of smartphones and tablets, mobile learning has become an increasingly popular way to engage students in language learning. Language learning apps, podcasts, and games allow learners to practice their language skills on the go, making it more convenient and accessible for students to immerse themselves in the target language. use of audio, video, and interactive online resources can enhance language learning. Learners can practice listening comprehension, pronunciation, and vocabulary through podcasts, online videos, language learning apps, and interactive exercises. This approach puts emphasis on learning and acquiring vocabulary in chunks and collocations, with the goal of increasing fluency and accuracy in language use *Authentic Materials* using authentic texts, videos, and audios (such as news articles, podcasts, and films) from the target language's culture to expose learners to real language use *Language Learning Management Systems* specialized platforms tailored for language learning to manage coursework, assessments, and progress tracking. combines online and face-to-face learning. Learners have access to digital tools and resources for self-study, while also attending traditional classes for interactive activities, feedback, and guidance from teachers. adaptive learning systems and AI-powered tools to tailor language learning materials and activities to the specific needs and preferences of the learner, targeting specific areas of improvement. Adopting a social approach involves creating opportunities for learners to interact

with each other in the target language, both inside and outside the classroom. This can be done through group projects, language cafes, language exchange platforms, and online communities.

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR): These emerging technologies offer immersive language learning experiences by simulating real-life environments and scenarios in the target language. VR and AR can transport students to different cultural settings, providing a powerful tool for developing language skills in context and enhancing cultural understanding. students learn the content at home through interactive, engaging materials, and class time is then used for activities, discussions, and application of the learned material. specialized platforms tailored for language learning to manage coursework, assessments, and progress tracking. social approach involves creating opportunities for learners to interact with each other in the target language, both inside and outside the classroom. This can be done through group projects, language cafes, language exchange platforms, and online communities. Language Learning Software with AI: Personalized learning experiences that adapt to individual student needs and learning styles, often providing instant feedback and tailored exercises. By incorporating these methods, approaches, and technologies, modern language learning can be made more engaging, relevant, and effective, while also fostering a deeper understanding of the cultural and linguistic nuances of the target language. Language Exchange/ Tandem Learning: Learners partner with native speakers of the target language to practice conversational skills. They take turns speaking in each other's languages, providing mutual support and feedback. Virtual Reality Emerging technologies like virtual reality can create immersive language learning experiences. Learners can practice language skills in virtual environments that simulate realistic scenarios, building both language competence and cultural understanding. Engaging in language exchange partnerships with native speakers through online communities, social media, and language exchange apps to practice conversation and gain specific cultural insights. video conferencing and online

platforms to connect learners with virtual tutors and language coaches who can provide personalized guidance and feedback for specific language learning goals. Augmented reality and virtual reality Incorporating virtual reality and technologies to create interactive and immersive language learning experiences, allowing learners to engage with specific cultural and linguistic content in a more engaging way. Online platforms with adaptive learning technology analyze individual learners' strengths and weaknesses and offer personalized learning paths. These platforms provide tailored content, exercises, and feedback to address each learner's specific needs.

Gamification By integrating game elements into language learning activities, gamification can make the language learning process more engaging and enjoyable for students. Language learning games and simulations can motivate students to practice and apply their language skills in a fun and interactive way. combines online and face-to-face learning. Learners have access to digital tools and resources for self-study, while also attending traditional classes for interactive activities, feedback, and guidance from teachers. Incorporating game elements, such as challenges, rewards, and leaderboards, can make language learning more engaging and motivating. Language learning apps and platforms often use gamification techniques to create interactive and enjoyable learning experiences.

In conclusion, the modern foreign language learning landscape is continuously evolving with new methodologies and technologies to support students in their language acquisition journey. Educators and learners can take advantage of these innovative approaches to create more effective and engaging language learning experiences. By leveraging these methods, ways, and technologies, language learners can develop their language skills in a more natural, immersive, and personalized manner. modern foreign language learning can be organized using a variety of methods, ways, and technologies. The key is to create engaging and interactive learning experiences that focus on developing communication skills in real-life contexts.

List of used literature

1. "The Multilingual Turn: Implications for SLA, TESOL, and Bilingual Education" by Stephen D. Krashen.
2. "Technology and Second Language Acquisition" edited by Carol A. Chapelle and Shannon Sauro.
3. "Task-Based Language Learning and Teaching" by Rod Ellis.
4. "Language Learning with Technology: Ideas for Integrating Technology in the Classroom" by Graham Stanley.
5. "The Routledge Handbook of Language Learning and Technology" edited by Fiona Farr and Liam Murray.
6. "Teaching and Learning Languages with Technology" by Carol A. Chapelle and Joan Jamieson.
7. "Language Learning Online: Towards Best Practice" by Felix Unger and Lutz M. Berkner.
8. "Digital Games in Language Learning and Teaching" edited by Hayo Reinders and Tereza Zawilinski.